

Thiopegan Derivatives. Part XXXII. Synthesis of 4-Carboxy-4,11-thiopegan Derivatives

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Derivatives of 10-methyl- and 10-phenyl-4-carboxy-4, 11-thiopegans have been synthesised by the condensation of *N*-acetylisisatinic acid and *N*-benzoylisisatinic acid, respectively, with β -mercapto-ethylamines or their hydrochlorides in presence of sodium acetate.

In an earlier communication¹ we have reported the synthesis of 4,11-thiopegans (I: R=Me, Ph; R'=COOMe, COOEt; R''=H). The introduction of a free COOH group (present in penicillins) is important from antibacterial activity point of view. So it was considered worthwhile to synthesise 4-carboxy-4,11-thiopegan derivatives (I: R=Me or Ph; R' = H, COOH, COOMe, COOEt; R'' = COOH).

(I)

N-Acetylisisatinic acid² (II: R=Me) condensed with β -mercapto-ethylamine (III: R'=H) to furnish 4-carboxy-10-methyl-4,11-thiopega-9-ene (I:R=Me; R'=R''=H; R''=COOH). When hydrochloride of (III) was used, condensation was carried out in presence of sodium acetate.

Likewise, the 10-phenyl derivatives of (I:R=Ph) were obtained by the condensation of *N*-benzoylisisatinic acid⁴ (II: R=Ph) with β -mercapto-ethylamine or hydrochlorides (III). For introducing Me group at position 6 of these thiopegan derivatives (I: R'''=Me), *N*-acetyl-5-methylisisatinic acid (II: R=R'''=Me) and *N*-benzoyl-5-methylisisatinic acid⁵ (II: R=Ph; R''' = Me) were condensed with β -mercapto-ethylamines(III). The general route pursued for this synthetic approach and its probable mechanism is depicted below:

1. Narang *et al.*, this *Journal* (communicated).
2. Suida, *Ber.*, 1891, 11, 584.
3. Shirley, "Preparation of Organic Intermediates", John Wiley & Sons, p. 189.
4. Schotten, *Ber.*, 1891, 24, 772.
5. Bischler and Muntendam, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 723.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Carboxy-10-methyl-4,11-thiopega-9-ene (I: R=Me; R''=COOH; R'=R'''=H).—Dry hydrogen sulphide gas was passed through a solution of ethyleneimine (2.2 g.) in anhydrous ethanol (30 ml) for 3 hr. To this was added *N*-acetylisatinic acid (II: R'''=H; R=Me; 4g.) in ethanol (25 ml) and the contents were refluxed on a water bath. The white product separating after $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. was refluxed for 1 hr. more. The product obtained was crystallised from water, m.p. 183°, yield 3.1 g. (65.8%).

4-Carboxy-3-methoxycarbonyl-10-methyl-4,11-thiopega-9-ene (I: R=Me; R'=CO₂Me; R''=COOH; R'''=H).—*N*-Acetylisatinic acid (II: R=Me; R'''=H; 1.4 g.) was dissolved in ethanol (8 ml) and to this was added hydrochloride of the methyl ester of (-)-cysteine (III: R'=CO₂Me; 1.14 g.) and sodium acetate (0.9 g.), dissolved in water (6 ml). The mixture was refluxed on a water bath. Separation of the white product started after $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. It was refluxed for an hour more and the product crystallised from ethanol in white needles, m.p. 220° (0.7 g., 34.3%).

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TABLE I

Synthesis of 4-carboxy-4,11-thiopegen derivatives.

Isotinic acid used.	P r o d u c t.			M.P.	Cryst. from.	Formula.	Found.	Reql.
	R.	R''.	R'''.					
Me	H	Me	H	183°	Water	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ S	N : 12.00%	11.20%
"	H	Me	-CO ₂ Me	220°	EtOH	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂ S	C : 55.18 H : 4.59 S : 10.55 N : 9.58	54.90 4.57 10.45 9.15
Ph	H	Ph	H	170°	AcOH	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	N : 8.63	9.03
"	H	"	-CO ₂ H	210°	"	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	N : 8.12	7.91
"	H	"	-CO ₂ Et	170-71°	"	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ S	N : 7.14 S : 7.73	7.33 8.37
"	Me	"	H	190°	EtOH	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	N : 8.27	8.64
"	"	"	-CO ₂ Me	160°	AcOH	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	S : 9.40	9.44
Me	"	Me	-CO ₂ H	205°	EtOH (dil.)	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂ S	C : 54.64 H : 4.55 S : 10.41	54.80 4.57 10.46
"	"	"	-CO ₂ Me	205°	AcOH	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	C : 56.23 H : 5.66	56.25 5.00

The other thiopegan derivatives, recorded in Table I, were prepared by either of the above two methods, depending on the nature of (III) (*i.e.*, whether it is the amine or its hydrochloride).

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